

CDC ROUND UP

JANUARY TO MARCH 2026

Civic Health
Innovation Labs

LIVERPOOL
CITY REGION
COMBINED AUTHORITY

The Civic Data Cooperative celebrates the end of five years of data stewardship

FESTIVAL OF DATA: A THREE-DAY CELEBRATION OF CREATIVITY, COMMUNITY AND CIVIC INNOVATION

Thank you to everyone who joined us from 5–7 February for the Festival of Data, celebrating the Civic Data Cooperative's landmark five-year programme. The three-day festival welcomed schoolchildren, professionals and families from across to explore how data and AI can improve public services and everyday life.

Organised in partnership with the Liverpool City Region Combined Authority and delivered by the CDC, a flagship research project from the Civic Health Innovation Labs at the University of Liverpool (CHIL), the festival highlighted how data can be used responsibly and collaboratively to improve lives across the region, and introduced visitors to the varying and novel ways the CDC and partners are embracing cutting-edge advancements in machine learning to improve lives.

Highlights included:

- Seven newly commissioned artworks, co-created by Year 6 schoolchildren and artists where data was transformed into imaginative art installations.
- A full-day conference on Public Service Transformation Through Data, featured thought-provoking talks from leaders including Chief AI Officer Tiffany St James.
- The Cabaret of Dangerous Data Ideas brought lighthearted and bold ideas to the stage.
- A free family-friendly exhibition, complete with Lego workshops, games, VR demos, and a Data Art Safari that engaged the community to think about how data shows up in their lives.

The festival also marked the end of the Civic Data Cooperative in its' current form. As Professor Buchan noted, the CDC's five-year journey has shown what is possible when communities, researchers and innovators come together with a common purpose.

Community Data and AI Charter Roadshow

The CDC team completed a roadshow of our Community Data and AI Charter work presenting this innovative data stewardship project at academic conferences, policy events, and in training sessions.

The roadshow included:

- Two events with Cabinet Office
- The LCR CA Technical Advisory group
- Halton Borough Council
- ADRUK Conference in Cardiff
- HDRUK Conference in Glasgow
- The LCR AI Summit
- The Youth AI Summit
- The University of Bath
- The Liverpool Leadership Networking Event
- The University of Manchester
- Government launch of GDS Local

Alongside the roadshow, we have published a [how to guide for data professionals](#). The Charter has also successfully been incorporated into data projects in the Wirral and NHS systems.

Launch of our independent evaluation report

The Civic Data Cooperative (CDC) unveiled its first independent Economic Evaluation Report at the CDC Festival Conference Day, marking a major milestone in demonstrating the value of civic data for the Liverpool City Region. The report, produced by Oxford Insights with support from Lateral Economics, offered the most rigorous external assessment to date of the CDC's work and confirmed that the programme has generated significant economic, social, and public health benefits since its inception.

According to the evaluation, the CDC delivered a return of between £3.96 and £8.87 for every £1 invested, even under intentionally conservative modelling. This strong performance reflected the CDC's role in enabling major linked datasets including CIPHA, M-RIC, and the C-GULL cohort and its contribution to over £55 million in competitive research funding secured for the region. The report also highlighted the CDC's wider civic contribution: building trusted data governance frameworks, advancing public and patient involvement, and laying the foundations for Liverpool's emerging learning health system.

Download [the full report](#)

Travel

CDC Director Joined UK Delegation to Vietnam for Landmark Health MOU in January 2026

On 28 January 2026, as part of a UK delegation to Ho Chi Minh City, our Director, Gary Leeming (Deputy Director, Civic Health Innovation Labs & Director, Civic Data Cooperative), participated in the signing of a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) that aims to advance healthcare collaboration between the Liverpool City Region and HCMC.

The MOU was formally signed by Professor Iain Buchan, Director of the Civic Health Innovation Labs, reflecting the official partnership between the two regions.

What's next?

The CDC in its current form is coming to an end on 31st March 2026 after five years of projects, engagement, and events all aimed at strengthening civic data stewardship across the Liverpool City Region. Over the next few months, we will continue to publish our final reports on the CDC's work including additional evaluation, summary reports, and academic publications.

Some of our programme team have already moved, or will soon transition, into new roles within the University of Liverpool or external organisations. They take with them our learning, collaborative ethos, and commitment to open working that have shaped the CDC's approach. We wish them every success and look forward to staying connected.

Other colleagues will continue their work within the LCR Combined Authority-funded Civic HealthTech Innovation Zone (CHI-Zone) programme. Key CDC legacy projects, including the LCR Digital Commons, technical support team, LCR Community of Practice, and the LCR Community Charter for Data and AI, will transition into this new programme to ensure continuity and long-term impact. Stay tuned for updates on those projects by following @CivicHealthInnovationLabs and @CHI-Zone on LinkedIn.

Thank you for your support throughout the five years of the CDC programme! We will keep you on our mailing list for future events and activities. If you would prefer not to receive updates on our ongoing work, please contact us via CHIL chil@liverpool.ac.uk.

